

Synthesis of some Acetylbiphenyl Derivatives and the Beckmann Rearrangement of their Oximes

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The Fries migration of 2,2'-diacetoxy and 2,2',4,4'-tetraacetoxybiphenyl and the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dihydroxy-, 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy-, 2,2'- and 4,4'- dimethoxy, 2,2',4,4'- and 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxybiphenyl have been studied. The acetyl derivatives obtained have been oxidised to acids of known structures. The di-oximes of the diacetyl derivatives on Beckmann rearrangement with PPA gave the corresponding diacetamido derivatives. These on hydrolysis gave the diamino derivatives which have also been prepared by the reduction of the corresponding dinitro compounds which in turn were obtained from the relevant methoxybiphenyls by nitration.

In continuation of the previous work on biphenyl derivatives¹, some acetyl derivatives of biphenyls have been synthesised.

2,2'-Diacetoxybiphenyl² on Fries migration with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 110–120° gave 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl. The same product was obtained on Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dihydroxybiphenyl with acetyl chloride at 120° in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. On methylation it gave the dimethyl ether which was identical with the product obtained on Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl. On oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 , the dimethoxydiacetylbiphenyl gave 2,2'-dimethoxy biphenyl 5,5'-dicarboxylic acid which was identical with the product obtained on oxidation of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di (chloromethyl) biphenyl³.

4,4'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on Friedel-Crafts acetylation afforded the 3,3'-diacetyl derivative as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained on methylation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl prepared by the Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetoxybiphenyl according to Boon-Long⁴.

2,2',4,4'-Tetraacetoxybiphenyl⁵ on Fries migration with anhydrous aluminium chloride by heating the mixture at 130–40° on or keeping in nitrobenzene at room temperature afforded 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl which gave a tetramethyl ether. This was also obtained on Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl. On oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 it gave 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained on oxidation of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-di(chloromethyl)biphenyl¹. An isomeric product isolated from the reaction

1. B. Kanakalakshmi, K. P. Mathai and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 469.
2. Y. Sugii, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1929, **50**, 183; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1930, **24**, 3505.
3. K. P. Mathai and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 347.
4. N. Boon-Long, *J. Pharm. Assoc. Siam*, 1948, **1**, No. 4, 5; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1949, **43**, 5017.
5. R. Meyer and K. Desmari, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 2814.

mixture has been tentatively assigned the 3,3'-diacetyl structure as the m.p. of this product is in close agreement with the same product obtained by Apsimon *et al.*⁶ by a different method. 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy-3,3',5,5'-tetraacetylbiphenyl was also isolated from the reaction mixture. This was also obtained when the Friedel-Crafts acetylation was carried out on 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxybiphenyl at 110–120° in an oil bath.

2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxybiphenyl on Friedel-Crafts acetylation gave 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetyl biphenyl which on oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 furnished 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid as seen by direct comparison with the acid obtained on oxidation of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-di(chloromethyl)biphenyl¹.

Smith⁷ carried out the Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime of 2-benzoyl biphenyl using phosphorus pentachloride and obtained 2-benzamido biphenyl and biphenyl anilide. The same rearrangement when carried out at a higher temperature in the presence of PPA gave fluorenone anil and 9-phenyl phenanthridine. The present work deals with the Beckmann rearrangement of the di-oximes of the diacetyl derivatives described above.

The di-oxime of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetyl biphenyl on heating with PPA on a steam bath gave the 5,5'-diacetamidobiphenyl which on hydrolysis with HCl (1 : 1) furnished the 5,5'-diaminobiphenyl as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained on reduction of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-dinitrobiphenyl prepared by the nitration of 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl according to Borsche and Scholten⁸.

The di-oxime of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl on a similar rearrangement gave the 3,3'-diacetamido derivative⁹ which on hydrolysis with conc. HCl gave the known 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diaminobiphenyl⁹ as seen by direct comparison with the product prepared according to Hodgson *et al.*⁹.

The di-oxime of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl on rearrangement with PPA gave 5,5'-diacetamido biphenyl which on hydrolysis with conc. HCl gave 5,5'-diamino derivative. This was identical with the product obtained on nitration of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl and reduction of the dinitro derivative formed with stannous chloride and HCl. This confirms that the dinitro derivative is 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-dinitrobiphenyl.

The di-oxime of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetylbiphenyl on Beckmann rearrangement afforded the 4,4'-diacetamido derivative which on hydrolysis with conc HCl gave the 4,4'-diamino derivative¹⁰. The same diamino derivative was also prepared by the nitration of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy biphenyl with conc. HNO_3 at 0° and reduction of the dinitro derivative obtained with stannous chloride and HCl. The dinitro derivative is therefore 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-dinitro biphenyl. When fuming, HNO_3 was used a tetranitro

6. J. W. Apsimon, N. G. Greasey, W. Marlow, K. Y. Sim and W. B. Whalley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4156.
7. P. A. S. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 431.
8. W. Borsche and B. G. B. Scholtn, *Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 607.
9. H. H. Hodgson and P. F. Holt., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 38.
10. A. Baessler, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 2126.

derivative was obtained which is tentatively assigned the 4,4',6,6'-tetranitro structure as the dinitro derivative has the 4,4'-dinitro structure and the other likely positions for the entry of the nitro group would be the 6,6'-positions which are ortho to the methoxy groups in 5,5'-positions and meta to the nitro groups in 4- and 4'- positions.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl: 2,2'-Diacetoxybiphenyl¹ (2.7 g.; 0.01 *M*) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.01 *M*) and heated in an oil bath at 110–20° for 4 hr. ice cold HCl was then added and the product obtained crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 275°. Yield 1.4 g. (Found : C, 70.6; H, 5.3. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₄, C, 71.1; H, 5.2%).

The same product was obtained when a mixture of 2,2'-dihydroxybiphenyl (1.86 g.; 0.01 *M*) acetyl chloride (3.12 g.; 0.04 *M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 *M*) was heated in an oil bath at 110–20° and the product obtained on decomposition of the reaction mixture was extracted with NaOH and the alkali soluble product was reprecipitated by addition of HCl.

The alkali insoluble product was 2,2'-diacetoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl. It was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 150°. (Found : C, 67.6; H, 5.3. Calc. for C₂₀H₁₈O₆, C, 67.8; H, 5.1%).

The same product was obtained when 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl was refluxed with acetic anhydride in the presence of sodium acetate.

The di-(2,4-D.N.P.) of 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetyl biphenyl was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 300°. (Found : N, 17.7. Calc. for C₂₈H₂₂O₁₀N₈, N, 17.8%).

The dimethyl ether: 2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl (1 g.) was refluxed in acetone (50 ml.) with dimethyl sulphate (2 g.) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (10 g.) for 8 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on removal of acetone and addition of water, crystallised from benzene-light petroleum, m.p. 163°. (Found : C, 72.8; H, 6.1. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₈O₄; C, 72.5; H, 6.0%).

The same product was obtained when 2,2'-dimethoxy biphenyl (2.1 g.; 0.01 *M*) and acetyl chloride (3.1 g.; 0.04 *M*) in carbon disulphide solution was kept with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 *M*) below 10° for 1 hr. and the reaction mixture worked up as usual.

The di-(2,4-D.N.P.) crystallised from nitrobenzene m.p. > 310°. (Found : N, 16.8. C₃₀H₂₈N₈O₁₀, calc. for N, 17.0%).

Oxidation: The above diacetyl derivative was heated with KMnO₄ (1 g.) and NaOH (10 g. in 10 ml. water) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The 5,5'-dicarboxylic acid obtained on acidification of the reaction mixture was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 340°. Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained according to Mathai and Sethna³ was not depressed.

* All melting points are uncorrected.

2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl : *2,2',4,4'*-Tetraacetoxybiphenyl (3 g.; 0.01 *M*) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 *M*) and heated in an oil bath at 130–140° for 4 hr. or kept at room temperature for 24 hr. using nitrobenzene as solvent. The product obtained on working up as usual was extracted with ether. The ether soluble product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 236°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 63.4; H, 5.0. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$; C, 63.5; H, 4.6%).

The tetra methyl ether : prepared as usual by refluxing the above diacetyl derivative in acetone with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous K_2CO_3 was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 214°. (Found : C, 67.0; H, 6.1. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$; C, 67.0; H, 6.1%).

The same compound was also obtained when an externally cooled mixture of *2,2',4,4'*-tetramethoxybiphenyl (2.7 g.; 0.01 *M*), acetyl chloride (3.1 g.; 0.04 *M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 *M*) in carbon disulphide was stirred for 20 minutes, kept for 1 hr. below 10° and worked up as usual.

The di-(2,4-D.N.P.) was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 301°. (Found : N, 15.2. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{30}O_{12}N_8$; N, 15.6%).

Oxidation : The above biphenyl derivative (0.5 g.) was heated with $KMnO_4$ (2g.) and NaOH (10 g. in 10 ml. water) for 2 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 255°. Mixed m.p. with the *2,2',4,4'*-tetramethoxy-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid obtained by the oxidation of *2,2',4,4'*-tetramethoxy-5,5'-di(chloromethyl) derivative according to Kanakalakshmi *et al.*¹ was not depressed.

2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl : After separating *2,2',4,4'*-tetrahydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl as shown above, the insoluble part in ether was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 245°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 63.8; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$; C, 63.5; H, 4.6%).

The tetra methyl ether : Prepared by refluxing the above diacetyl biphenyl (0.5 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) with dimethyl sulphate (3 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (15 g.) for 8 hr. on a steam bath was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 144°. (Found : C, 66.6; H, 5.9. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$; C, 67.0; H, 6.1%).

Apsimon *et al.*⁶ who prepared *2,2',4,4'*-tetrahydroxy 3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl and its tetramethyl ether by a different method gave m.ps. 248–49° and 136° respectively.

2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxy-3,3',5,5'-tetraacetylbiphenyl : After separating the two diacetyl derivatives from the Fries reaction mixture a product insoluble in xylene was obtained which crystallised from diphenylether, m.p. 302°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 62.4; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{26}O_8$; C, 62.2; H, 4.7%).

The same compound was obtained when a mixture of *2,2',4,4'*-tetrahydroxybiphenyl (2.2 g.; 0.01 *M*), acetyl chloride (3.1 g.; 0.04 *M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (9.3 g.; 0.07 *M*) was heated in an oil bath at 120° for 2 hr. and the reaction mixture worked up as usual.

The tetramethyl ether : prepared by refluxing the above tetraacetyl derivative (0.5 g.) in acetone (25 ml.) with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous K_2CO_3 for 8 hr. on a steam bath was crystallised from light petroleum. It gave m.p. 95° . (Found : C, 65.2; H, 6.0. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{26}O_8$; C, 65.1; H, 5.9%).

The tetra-oxime : Prepared as usual and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 150° (Found : N, 10.8. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{30}N_4O_8$; N, 11.1%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl : prepared by keeping a mixture of 4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl (2.1 g.; 0.01 M) in carbon disulphide (30 ml.), acetyl chloride (3.1 g.; 0.04 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 M) for 1 hr. below 10° and working up as usual was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 148° . Mixed m.p. with the product obtained on methylation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl, prepared according to Boon-Long⁴, was not depressed.

The di-(2,4-D.N.P.) : crystallised from nitrobenzenexylene mixture gave m.p. 302° . (Found : N, 16.7. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{26}N_8O_{10}$; N, 17.0%).

2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetylbiophenyl : To an externally cooled mixture of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxybiphenyl (2.7 g.; 0.01 M) and acetyl chloride (3.1 g.; 0.04 M) in carbon disulphide (30 ml.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g.; 0.04 M) was added. The product obtained on removal of carbon disulphide and decomposition of the mixture with cold dilute HCl was washed with NaOH and crystallised from xylene in white needles, m.p. 197° . (Found : C, 67.3; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$; C, 67.0; H, 6.1%).

The di-(2,4-D.N.P.) crystallised from nitrobenzene gave m.p. 299° . (Found : N, 15.7. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{30}N_8O_{12}$; N, 15.6%).

Oxidation : 2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetylbiophenyl (0.5 g.) was refluxed for 2 hr. with $KMnO_4$ (2 g.) and NaOH (10 g. in 10 ml. water). The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 255° . Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained on oxidation of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-di(chloromethyl)biphenyl¹ was not depressed.

The di-oxime of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl : 2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiophenyl (2 g.) in alcohol was added to a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2 g.) and KOH (1 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product obtained after removing the alcohol crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 269° . (Found : C, 66.0; H, 6.3; N, 8.2. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{22}N_2O_4$; C, 65.9; H, 6.1; N, 8.5%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetamidobiphenyl : The above dioxime (0.5 g.) was mixed with PPA (30 g.) and the reaction mixture protected from moisture was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. Ice cold water was then added that the product which separated was thoroughly washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 247° . (Found : C, 65.5; H, 6.0; N, 8.7. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_4$; C, 65.9; H, 6.1; N, 8.5%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diaminobiphenyl : The diacetamido derivative (0.2 g.) was heated with HCl (1 : 1; 5 ml.) for 3 hr. on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was neutralised with NaOH and the product obtained crystallised from toluene, m.p. 162° . (Found : C, 68.8; H, 6.6; N, 10.9. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{16}N_2O_2$; C, 68.8; H, 6.5; N, 11.4%).

The same diamino derivative was synthesised for comparison by the reduction of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-dinitrobiphenyl prepared according to Borsche and Scholten⁸. The dinitrobiphenyl derivative (0.5 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and stannous chloride (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid with 2 drops of HCl was added to the above mixture. HCl gas was passed through the reaction mixture till the amine hydrochloride was precipitated. It was filtered, dissolved in water and neutralised with NaOH. The precipitated amino compound extracted with ether and crystallised from benzene. Mixed m.p. with the diamino derivative described above was not depressed.

The *di-oxime* of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl: Prepared as in the previous case from 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl (1 g.) in alcohol, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and KOH (0.5 g.) and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 6.2; N, 8.7. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}N_2O_4$; C, 65.9; H, 6.1; N, 8.5%).

4,4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-diacetamidobiphenyl: The di oxime (0.5 g.) was mixed with PPA (40 g.) and heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. It was diluted with water and the product obtained crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 340°. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 6.0; N, 8.6. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_4$; C, 65.9; H, 6.1; N, 8.5%).

The same diacetamidobiphenyl was prepared by Hodgson *et al.*⁹ by the acetylation of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diaminobiphenyl. They gave m.p. 330°.

Hydrolysis: The diacetamido derivative (0.2 g.) was heated with conc. HCl (5 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The aminehydrochloride obtained was neutralised with NaOH and the free base obtained crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 193°.

The same compound was prepared by Hodgson *et al.*⁹ by the reduction of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-dinitrobiphenyl using iron powder and glacial acetic acid. They gave m.p. 195°. The present authors used stannous chloride and HCl for this reduction. Mixed m.p. with the diamino derivative described above was not depressed.

The *di-oxime* of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl: Prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of 2,2',4,4'-tetramethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbiphenyl (1 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and KOH (0.5 g.) as before and crystallised from acetic acid gave m.p. 238°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 6.5; N, 7.6. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_6$; C, 61.9; H, 6.2; N, 7.2%).

2,2',4,4'-Tetramethoxy-5,5'-diacetamidobiphenyl: The above dioxime (0.5g.) and PPA (40 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. Ice cold water was added and the product obtained crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 61.7; H, 6.3; N, 7.1. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_6$; C, 61.9; H, 6.2; N, 7.2%).

2,2',4,4'-Tetramethoxy-5,5'-diaminobiphenyl: The diacetamido derivative (0.5 g.) was heated with HCl (1 : 1; 5 ml.) for 2 hr. on a steam bath. The reaction mixture on working up as before gave a product which crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 6.6; N, 9.1. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}N_2O_4$; C, 63.2; H, 6.2; N, 9.2%).

2,2',4,4'-Tetramethoxy-5,5'-dinitrobiphenyl: 2,2',4,4'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and the solution added to cold conc. HNO_3 (5 ml.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml.). The mixture was kept for 30 minutes and the product obtained on

pouring into water was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 288°. (Found : C, 53.0; H, 4.7; N, 7.5. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}N_2O_8$; C, 52.7; H, 4.4; N, 7.7%).

Reduction : The above dinitro derivative (0.5 g.) was added to stannous chloride (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml.) with two drops of conc. HCl and HCl gas was passed. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from benzene, m.p. 150°. Mixed m.p. with the product obtained from the hydrolysis of the diacetamido-biphenyl as described above was not depressed.

The di-oxime of 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetylbiphenyl : Prepared from 2,2',5,5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetylbiphenyl as before and crystallised from acetic acid gave m.p. 288°. (Found : C, 61.6; H, 6.0; N, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_6$; C, 61.9; H, 6.2; N, 7.2%).

2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-diacetamidobiphenyl : The above oxime (0.5 g.) mixed with PPA (30 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. Ice cold water was added and the product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 252°. (Found : C, 62.1; H, 6.5; N, 7.6. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_6$; C, 61.9; H, 6.2; N, 7.2%).

2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-diaminobiphenyl : The above diacetamido derivative (0.5 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. with HCl (1 : 1; 5 ml.). The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from xylene in white needles, m.p. 210°. (Found : C, 63.6; H, 6.4; N, 9.0. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}N_2O_4$; C, 63.2; H, 6.2; N, 9.2%).

Baessler¹⁰ prepared the same diamino compound by a different method and gave m.p. 210°.

2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-dinitrobiphenyl : 2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride and the reaction mixture cooled in ice. Conc. HNO_3 (2 ml.) in acetic anhydride (5 ml.) was slowly added by stirring. It was kept for 30 minutes in ice and then poured in water. The product obtained crystallised from xylene, m.p. 277°. (Found : C, 52.4; H, 4.6; N, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}N_2O_8$; C, 52.7; H, 4.4; N, 7.7%).

2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrobiphenyl : 2,2',5,5'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride and the reaction mixture was cooled in ice. Fuming HNO_3 (4 ml.) in acetic anhydride (5 ml.) was slowly added by stirring. It was kept for 2 hr. and then poured in water. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 221°. (Found : C, 42.5; H, 3.5; N, 12.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}N_4O_{12}$; C, 42.3; H, 3.1; N, 12.3%).

Reduction of the 4,4'-dinitro derivative : 4,4'-Dinitrobiphenyl (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid was added to stannous chloride (1 g.) in acetic acid (2 ml.) with 2 drops of conc. HCl. HCl gas was passed and the amino hydrochloride precipitated was treated with alkali to get a free base which was crystallised from xylene, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the 4,4'-diamino derivative described above was 210°.